

RESULTS ON CHARACTERISTIC VECTORS

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Abstract

In this paper we have established the bounds of the extreme characteristic roots of $n\text{lap}(G)$ and $s\text{Lap}(G)$ by their traces. Also found the bounds for n -th characteristic roots of $n\text{Lap}(G)$ and $s\text{Lap}(G)$.

Key words : characteristic root, Normalized laplacian matrix, signless laplacian matrix.

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1. Introduction

let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph with $|v| = n$ and $|E| = e$.

k_i denote the degree of u_i for $u_i \in V$

m_i is the set of neighbours of u_i

$i \sim j$ denote the adjacent of u_i and u_j .

$Adj(G)$ denote the adjacency matrix.

$Lap(G)$ denote the laplacian matrix.

$dig(G)$ denote the diagonal matrix.

It is clear $Lap(G) = dig(G) - Adj(G)$

Definition–1 Normalized Laplacian matrix:

let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph then the Normalized laplacian matrix of G is denoted by $nLap(G)$ and given by

$nLap(G) = [r_{ij}]_{mm}$ where

$$\begin{aligned} r_{ij} &= 1 : i = j \\ &= \frac{-1}{\sqrt{k_i k_j}} : i \sim j \\ &= 0 : \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

Definition–2 Signless Laplacian matrix:

let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph then the Signless laplacian matrix of G is denoted by $sLap(G)$ and given by

$sLap(G) = [s_{ij}]_{mm}$ where

$$\begin{aligned} s_{ij} &= k_i : i = j \\ &= 1 : i \sim j \\ &= 0 : \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

Since $nlap(G)$ is real symmetric matrix and characteristic roots of $nlap(G)$ is denoted by

$\mu_1(nlap(G)) \geq \dots \geq \mu_m(nlap(G))$ and

$slap(G)$ is also real symmetric matrix and characteristic roots of $slap(G)$ is denoted by

$\mu_1(nlap(G)) \geq \dots \geq \mu_m(nlap(G))$.

Following theorem-1.1 and theorem-1.2 are used to find bounds for characteristic roots of $\text{nlap}(G)$ and $\text{slap}(G)$.

Theorem-1.1 Let V and $\mu = [\mu_j]$ be non zero column vectors, $e=(1,1,1,\dots,1)^T$, $n=\frac{\mu^T e}{m}$, $B=I_m - \frac{ee^T}{m}$, $s^2 = \frac{\mu^T B \mu}{m}$ and I_m is a unit matrix. Let $\mu_m \leq \dots \leq \mu_2 \leq \mu_1$ then,

$$-s\sqrt{mV^T B V} \leq V^T \mu - mV^T e = V^T B \mu \leq s\sqrt{mV^T B V}$$

$$\sum(\mu_i - \mu_m)^2 = m[s^2 + (n - \mu_m)^2]$$

$$\sum(\mu_1 - \mu_j)^2 = m[s^2 + (\mu_1 - \mu_n)^2]$$

$$\mu_m \leq n - \frac{s}{\sqrt{m-1}} \leq n + \frac{s}{\sqrt{m-1}} \leq \mu_1.$$

Theorem-1.2 Let B be $m \times m$ with complex entries. A^+ is conjugate transpose of A . Let $B = AA^+$ whose characteristic roots are $\mu_m(C) \leq \dots \leq \mu_2(C) \leq \mu_1(C)$ Then

$$n - s\sqrt{m-1} \leq \mu_m^2(C) \leq n - \frac{s}{\sqrt{m-1}}.$$

$$n + \frac{s}{\sqrt{m-1}} \leq \mu_m^2(1) \leq n + s\sqrt{m-1}.$$

Where $\frac{\text{Trace}(e^2)}{m} - n = s^2$ and $\frac{\text{Trace}(B)}{m} = n$.

2. Main Results

Theorem–2.1 Let G is simple graph, $nLap(G)$ is normalized laplacian matrix with characteristic roots $\mu_m(nLap(G)) \leq \dots \leq \mu_2(nLap(G)) \leq \mu_1(nLap(G))$ Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_m(nLap(G)) &\leq \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} + \sqrt{\frac{trace[lap(G)]^4 - mn^2}{m(m-1)}}\right)} \\ \mu_1(nLap(G)) &\geq \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} + \sqrt{\frac{trace[lap(G)]^4 - mn^2}{m(m-1)}}\right)} \\ \mu_1(nLap(G)) &\leq \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{trace[lap(G)]^4}{n} - n^2\right)(m-1)}\right)} \end{aligned}$$

Proof : It is obvious

$$Trace(nLap(G))^2 = m + 2 \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} \text{ and}$$

$$Trace(nLap(G))^4 = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(1 + \sum_{i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j}\right)^2 + 2 \sum_{i<j} \left(\sum_{k \in m_i \cap m_j} \frac{1}{k_k \sqrt{k_i k_j}} - \sum_{i\sim j} \frac{2}{\sqrt{k_i k_j}}\right)^2$$

Since $nLap(G)$ is real symmetric matrix, we found result from theorem–1.2.

Illustration–2.2 Let $G = (V, E)$, $V = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$, $E = \{(5, 6), (4, 5), (3, 5), (3, 4), (2, 6), (2, 4), (2, 3), (1, 5), (1, 2)\}$ Then

$\mu(nlap(G))$	[4]	[7] above bound	[6]below bound
1.86	2	1.93	1.34

Theorem–2.3 Let G is simple graph, $sLap(G)$ is normalized laplacian matrix with characteristic roots $\mu_m(sLap(G)) \leq \dots \leq \mu_2(sLap(G)) \leq \mu_1(sLap(G))$ Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_m(sLap(G)) &\leq \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} + \sqrt{\frac{trace[lap(G)]^4 - mn^2}{m(m-1)}}\right)} \\ \mu_1(sLap(G)) &\geq \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} + \sqrt{\frac{trace[lap(G)]^4 - mn^2}{m(m-1)}}\right)} \\ \mu_1(sLap(G)) &\leq \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{trace[lap(G)]^4}{n} - n^2\right)(m-1)}\right)} \end{aligned}$$

Proof : It is obvious

$$Trace(sLap(G))^2 = m + 2 \sum_{i<j, i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j} \text{ and}$$

$$Trace(sLap(G))^4 = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(1 + \sum_{i\sim j} \frac{1}{k_i k_j}\right)^2 + 2 \sum_{i<j} \left(\sum_{k \in m_i \cap m_j} \frac{1}{k_k \sqrt{k_i k_j}} - \sum_{i\sim j} \frac{2}{\sqrt{k_i k_j}}\right)^2$$

Since $sLap(G)$ is real symmetric matrix, we found result from theorem–1.2.

Illustration–2.4 Let $G = (V, E)$, $V = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$, $E = \{(4, 6), (4, 5), (3, 5), (2, 3), (1, 7), (1, 6), (1, 5), (1, 4), (1, 3), (1, 2)\}$ Then

$\mu(\text{slap}(G))$	[3]	[2]	[1]	[10] above bound	[9] below bound
7.67	9.3	9.7	9.1	7.8	4.58

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS :

I have presented results on connecting the bounds of the extreme characteristic roots of normalized laplacian matrix and signless laplacian matrix. and using it found found the bounds for n-th characteristic roots of normalized and signless laplacian matrix.

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